

Pictograms for Sound Design: A Language for the Communication of Product Sounds

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Abstract

Sound designers often encounter problems in communicating a newly developed sound concept to other designers, researchers, engineers, and marketers. To support the communication of product sounds, a pictographic language has been designed to describe product sound events in such a way that it relates the physical properties of sounds to its perceptual properties. This new pictographic language will be presented and it will also be discussed how it facilitates the communication of a product sound.

Keywords: sound, language, pictograms, communication, tool

Visual information design

Visual information design is a very expansive field, which comprises interface design, music notation, warning and instruction design, sign language for hearing-impaired, etc. It provides fast and accurate communication in user interfaces and employs graphical representation systems such as icons, pictograms, and symbols. The amount of information and similarity decreases from icons to symbols compared to the original object/event. On the one hand, icons and pictograms represent events and objects within a context (e.g., Olympic games pictograms). On the other hand, symbols are abstract and arbitrary representations that require learning (e.g., the letters of the alphabet, the traffic sign ‘no parking’); and they might not refer to any existing objects or events. A visual language makes use of these graphical representation systems to enhance the communication. A spoken or written language would need much more elements (i.e., words) to indicate a certain object or event, whereas in a pictographic language, only one or two elements are needed, the information is more condensed or it is represented by a set of graphical features that are very typical. In addition, it enables communication between people with a different linguistic background. For example, in the airports, a right-arrow sign and a suitcase pictogram together construct a visual sentence, which means that the baggage service is located on the right hand side.

The term 'icon' has become to be associated with any functional images used in GUI (Graphical User Interface) designs after the emergence of desktop metaphors (e.g., Macintosh Finder). Icons represent programs, folders, functions, menus, etc. Interface designers have explored the use of sound in GUIs, as well. Gaver (1989) introduced the term 'auditory icons' for his SonicFinder design (an auditory interface developed for Apple Computer, Inc). His auditory icons represent the physical sounding objects (e.g., a trash can sounds like something fell into a metal trash can) and their function is similar to visual icons. Blattner, Sumikawa, and Greenberg (1989) used the term called 'earcons' to indicate abstract sounds or rhythmic musical patterns. Mynatt (1994) developed a design methodology for auditory icons; identifiability, conceptual mapping, physical parameters, and user preferences are the factors in this methodology. Edworthy and Adams (1996) pointed out that in the design of warning symbols, legibility, conspicuity, discriminability, and urgency mapping is required in order for people to comprehend and to learn the symbols. Holmes (2000/2001) discerned various conventions to design a set of pictograms (e.g., the overall shape, the style of drawings, the subject matter, the context, and the color).

Until now, the work in auditory icons has dealt with the sonification of the graphical objects or events in GUIs. Whereas in this study, pictograms, which belong to a certain sound aspect, have been designed to develop a pictographic language that visualizes sounds. The possibility of using of pictograms in a visual language will be explored in this paper. The sounds of products and the sound producing parts of products will be taken as a starting point for the design of pictograms. Therefore, the perceptual and physical qualities of sound and image should be investigated.

Product sound quality

Product sound design incorporates the sound in the design of a product to increase the product acceptability amongst users. Pursuing the new developments in engineering, technology, production techniques, chemistry of the materials, and marketing strategies, a product sound designer tries to estimate the users' expectation of the product -at the design stage- and to adapt the sound quality to a desired one. In addition, because of the new insights in human perception and emotional experience of sound, producers have come to realize that product sounds have high-level affective influences on user experiences of a product. For

example, adjusting the sound pressure level in car interiors may influence users' emotional experiences upon the car. The new sound might indicate a pleasant ride, an expensive car, or a tolerable noise level.

Traditionally, product sounds have been treated as noise; and engineers have only been concerned with the reduction of the sound pressure level emitted by a product (noisy product) to a level that it does not annoy users. Recently, the complexity of the requirements to design a product as well as a product sound has increased due to the producers' demands on cost effectivity, time efficiency, environmental friendliness, up-to-date design; and due to the new insights in human perception and emotional experience. Furthermore, recent available technology allows designers to seek and discover the cause of an undesirable sound. Subsequently, they replace the problematic part of the product with a suitable one.

In the recent definition of product sound quality, Blauert and Jekosch (1997) argue that product sound quality is a result of judgments on auditory characteristics of a product sound performed by a user. The mood of a user may influence the perceived product quality, as well as the perceived product sound quality may influence the actual emotional state of the user depending upon the cognitive judgments.

The recent definition of product sound quality contradicts the traditional view in the sense that the sound caused by a product cannot always be treated as noise. Moreover, it may signify functionality, feedback, luxury, comfort, ease, attention, and brand value depending on user expectations of a product. In a user study, the results showed that the truck drivers prefer to receive feedback sound from the engine while they are driving instead of a sound attenuated truck interior design (Talamo, 1982). Moreover, brands like Harley Davidson or Grolsch especially use sound as a brand value, which may exemplify the impact of product sounds on users.

Sound quality in physical terms

Sound is the result of fluctuations in air pressure. It is expressed in decibels (sound intensity), amplitude (sound pressure), frequency (the variation rate of air pressure), etc. Sound quality is often described in terms of psychoacoustical measures. Loudness, roughness, noisiness, sharpness, brightness, and pitch are some of the commonly used psychoacoustical attributes that determine the auditory sensory pleasantness (Zwicker and Fastl, 1990). To measure these

psychoacoustical attributes, the physical parameters of product sounds need to be known. By doing so, a product sound designer can determine what range of sounds elicits the auditory sensory pleasantness (or unpleasantness).

Sound is a time-dependent percept. Therefore, the physical parameters of a sound are calculated over time and depicted on a timeline. Waveforms reflect the pressure variations as a function of time; and sonograms show the frequency distribution in time. However, these representations do not disclose the functions and the usage process of products. In addition, it is almost impossible to derive perceptual or experiential aspects of a sound from the shape of its waveform. Although, these visual representations facilitate the communication of product sound to a certain extent in physical terms, such representations still require the perceptually related information flow.

Perceived sound quality

Not much is known about how people perceive product sounds. However, several researchers investigated the timbral properties of sound. Solomon (1958) found relevant descriptive adjectives that could be used to characterize passive sonar sounds. Von Bismarck (1974) found perceptual dimensions underlying verbal attributes that described the timbre of steady state sounds, of which sharpness was the most important. Björk (1985) investigated the emotional dimensions associated with auditory sensation. The results revealed that roughness, sharpness-pitch, and loudness sensations were correlated with evaluation, activity, and potency dimensions respectively. Kendall and Carterette (1993) used the verbal attributes of Von Bismarck's adjectives to describe the timbre of musical instruments, and concluded that those adjectives were not appropriate for the purpose. It has also been argued that psychoacoustical terms 'sharpness' and 'roughness' were associated with 'pleasantness' of the sound (Zwicker and Fastl, 1990).

Other researchers have investigated the identification of sound and its sources. Bregman (1990) proposed two important concepts that underlie the mental process of how people come to perceive events: auditory stream segregation, and/or auditory stream integration.

McAdams (1993) discussed in detail the auditory recognition process and suggested that auditory recognition and auditory identification are two separate but consecutive stages. With respect to the cognitive aspects of sounds, Bartlett (1977) investigated the role of verbalization in memory for environmental sounds and showed that people could recognize

the labels and sources of environmental sounds. In another study, Ballas (1993) showed that identification time, occurrence frequency, and cognitive aspects of everyday sounds play important roles in identification of sources of everyday sounds. A recent study by Kunkler-Peck and Turvey (2000) indicated that one could hear the shape, size, and material of thin plates.

Gaver's (1993a) research on the categorization of sounds is of interest for the present study. He discerned three categories for sound producing events: sounds of vibrating objects, liquid sounds, and aerodynamic sounds. Still, this categorization may not be sufficient to define the domain of product sounds. Gaver (1993b), also, described the physics of sound-producing events to provide an initial orientation towards the relevant attributes of sound-producing events. He concluded that different type of impacts elicits different frequency range of sounds depending on the material, stiffness, and medium of the impacting objects.

The interdisciplinary communication problem of product sounds

In the course of the product design process, experts from several areas provide knowledge to contribute to the overall design project. To improve the design quality, a continuous information flow can be observed among these experts. An industrial engineer is responsible for the feasibility of the whole project, whereas a mechanical engineer may deal with the manufacturing techniques regarding the material choice. An industrial design engineer decides how the product should function and what kind of mechanical/electrical part would result better in the product functionality. A marketer defines the marketing strategies for the product acceptability amongst the target group. An advertiser communicates the values of the product to the potential users.

In this team, a sound designer participates in the design process of a product when a new sound concept needs to be introduced to the overall design concept of the product. The task of the product sound designer may vary from solving the roughness problem in the sound of a domestic appliance to translating the total design concept of a product into sound design. By doing so, the sound designer needs to communicate with engineers about, for example, the engine materials in order to evoke efficiency, expensiveness, comfort, etc. In the following example, a description of the sound design problems of a product is presented (Fog and Pedersen, 1999).

“A car-maker wanted a silent power-steering with a faint quality sound. The sub-supplier asked for an analysis of the sound from the existing power-steering systems, and specifications of the desired “sound” and suggestions to design changes. As a result of this project, new owners of that make can pride themselves on the quiet and harmonious sound of their power-steering.”

The multidisciplinary nature of the product design process requires precise, effective, and dynamic information flow; therefore, no vague, misspelled, arbitrary communication types can be afforded. However, it is difficult to describe the properties of sounds, either verbally or graphically, because a common verbal language (i.e., lexicon) is missing. For example, descriptive words like ‘rough’, ‘soft’, or ‘round’ do not immediately relate to a specific property in sound. Many products exist causing ‘rough’ sound such as shavers, epilators, etc. Moreover, a semantic problem exists in sound descriptions. Rough and soft are tactile sensory percepts, and round is a visual one. It was also shown (Martens and Giragama, 2002) that the words used to describe guitar timbres in Japanese and Sinhalese languages (with the same English meanings, e.g., pleasant, cheerful, sharp) were related to different acoustical dimensions in those languages. This may indicate a language problem. Yet, a sound designer needs to discuss some attributes of the product sound with the engineers, marketeers, or other designers who are involved in the design process. Supposedly, this multidisciplinary team has insight in the overall design concept of the product; however when discussing the sound-specific topics, they might not have sufficient background in auditory event perception and familiarity with sound-related technical terms (e.g. bark scales, modulation frequency, sones, phons, onset/offset envelopes, etc.)

Proposed solution: A pictographic language for the communication of product sounds

Why should the use of pictograms solve the above-mentioned communication problem? It is obvious that no verbal or graphical language can replace the percept of a sound. Hearing an actual sound evokes a different perceptual experience or associated meaning than having to imagine the sound on the basis of a verbal description. Therefore, the proposed pictographic language is not supposed to substitute existing percepts; instead, it is a design proposal to improve the existing communication for product sounds. A combination of sound and a pictographic language may communicate in a faster and more accurate way.

Pictograms for product sound design should represent the source that generated the sound. To be able to design such pictograms, insight in physical and perceptual product sound characteristics is required. In the physical space, product sounds originate from the moving (sliding, rotating, rinsing, etc.) and contacting (hitting, scraping, dropping) parts of the products, the engines, fans, buttons, etc. The frequencies radiated by a product depend on the material stiffness and the medium of the vibrating objects. The amount of force and the resonance properties applied to the moving or static product parts determine the sound pressure level (amplitude). In the perceptual space, product sounds are described in terms of relevant perceptual attributes. In auditory perception, it has been shown that people were able to perceive the material, size, and shape of sounding objects and describe the perceptual qualities of sounds (Hermes, 1998; Kunkler-Peck and Turvey, 2000; Klatzky, Pai, and Krotkov, 2000). Furthermore, product sounds elicit certain emotions that influence the total product perception (Västfjäll, 2002).

Pictograms and categorization

In a pictogram domain, the pictograms represent the sounds. As a first step, the domain of product sounds should be defined. Decomposing a product into its functions and its parts shows the type of sounds and sound sources are involved. For example, a vacuum cleaner has a plug for the electricity, power button to turn on/off, and speed adjustment button. These parts need interaction with the user and the sound comes out during or after the interaction. The engine and fan sound of the vacuum cleaner is generated at the stage of sucking and blowing air. The sucking/blowing sound changes its property depending on the speed of the fan and engine. These types of engine sounds are intrinsic sounds; they occur when the product is running. After decomposing the products into its functions and its parts, the underlying perceptual product sound categories should be defined. This requires the listeners' perceptual and cognitive judgments upon the product sounds. Therefore, Özcan, van Egmond, and Jacobs (submitted, 2004) investigated the underlying dimensions of perceptually relevant product sound categories. Do users categorize by sound source, by product type, by sounds' physical or psychophysical attributes, by affective responses? These aspects will determine the type of pictograms (including icons, pictograms, and/or symbols) used in the pictographic language.

In a category, the extent of similarity among the members differs. Therefore, the difference in

similarity among members should be reflected in the design of the members of the pictogram groups. Each group covers certain product sounds on different dimensions (i.e., the material interaction type may categorize button sounds; whereas, the amount of impact absorbed by the material and the material stiffness may categorize impact sounds). One member of a category exists that is more similar to all other category members. This member may represent the whole category (Mervis and Rosch, 1981). Consequently, the most representative pictograms should be designed in such a way that they represent the groups. Mervis and Rosch observed a hierarchical organization among categories. Similarly, the pictogram categories are organized at a basic level and a sub-ordinate level. The possible organization of pictograms is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1, Relationship among pictograms in a group

The scenario

Imagine that the following problems with sound have been encountered in the design process of a vacuum cleaner, and the sound designer has to explain this problem to the project manager.

“The usability tests revealed that the vacuum cleaner has an unexpected loud sound just 2-3 seconds after it starts running. Most of the users had the impression that the machine got broken at that time, hearing the sound was annoying, and the sound was uncontrolled. The sound designer doesn’t know which part causes the loud sound; however, he has to fix it because the vacuum cleaner should sound expensive, accurate, and pleasant.”

As a first step, the sound designer records the sound of the vacuum cleaner to analyze the physical properties of the sound. The recorded sound (Figure 2) presents the relative amplitude of the vacuum cleaner sound as a function of time. This figure may reflect several events. In the figure, one short and one long event can be observed. The first event seems to have happened very abruptly and decayed in less than 100 milliseconds. The second event seems to have started fading-in and finished fading-out slowly. In addition, another peak, similar to the first event, has been observed in the second event near the end of the recording. Approximately at the 2nd second, the increased amplitude can be seen in the figure, and this indicates the users' complaints about the vacuum cleaner sound. However, this figure does not convey the auditory qualities of the sound. It is hard to imagine how this waveform would sound like. One cannot distinguish the sound of a vacuum cleaner from the sound of, for example, a microwave oven by just looking at the waveform of a sound recording.

Figure 2, Amplitude representation of the vacuum cleaner sound

In the second step, it is necessary to determine the perceptually relevant components of a product sound. The possible sound sources should be determined to find the part that makes the undesired sound. Therefore, the vacuum cleaner is decomposed into parts that generate sound. Three main sound sources exist in the function cycle: an on/off button, an engine, and a fan. The sound designer records the sounding parts separately to find out the problem. The user turns on the machine by pressing the on/off button. The engine and the fan start running, subsequently. The sound of an on/off button is followed by the engine and fan sounds. The user turns the machine off by pressing the button again. The engine and the fan stop running; but the fan sound takes longer to stop. After determining the sound sources and the processes, the sound designer selects the proper pictograms for the sounding parts. In Figure 3, the sound designer finally attaches the sound pictograms to the physical properties of sound (i.e., amplitude, in this case). The to-be-analyzed sound property can, of course, be replaced by other physical (e.g., sonogram) or psychophysical attributes (e.g., brightness, roughness, pitch etc.) properties of a sound.

Figure 3, Pictographic representation of the amplitude of the vacuum cleaner sound

Once the whole product sound is represented visually, the sound designer refers to the problem in a timeline. It was said that the loud sound started 2-3 seconds after the vacuum cleaner starts running. It seems that at that time, only the fan and the engine generates sound. However, the engine sound has a drastic change in the amplitude envelope at around 2nd second. Once the whole sound events and the problem is visualized by pictograms, the visualization of the sounds events can be printed and be used as a guide to show the problem. In design meetings, such a document may also serve as a reference tool for the designers, where there are only paper documents are available.

The design of the pictograms

The proposed pictographic language is still under development. Thus, some ideas may seem very vague. However, some effort has been put in designing some of the pictogram groups to see whether the proposed language would be applicable. The dimensions, which underlie the design criteria of a pictogram group, differ from one group to another because of the multidimensional nature of product sound quality. In Figure 1, the button sounds were visually represented. The button sounds are the cause of two interacting materials, and the stiffness of these materials determines the click sound. The metal-to-metal clicks generate a higher frequency sound than the plastic-to-plastic clicks. In the Figure 1, from top to bottom, stiffness of the lower interacting material increases, whereas, from left to right, stiffness of the upper interacting material increases. In Figure 4, for the same pictograms, the tone of the color indicates the stiffness of the material. The dark the colors indicate hard materials (e.g., metal, glass), the lighter colors indicate softer materials (e.g., rubber, plastic). These pictograms may represent, different kinds of button, and click sounds.

Figure 4, Various button pictograms

A categorization study might result in perceptual product sound groups and the hierarchy among them. In Figure 4, the possible subordinate level product sounds have been displayed, whereas, the possible basic level product sounds are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5, Basic level representative pictograms

Other application areas

Industrial designers and engineers often use CAD-systems to model their designs in 3D environments. 3D modeling is necessary for the first impressions of the design project. Generally, 3D modeled product designs expose an almost real look-and-feel of the product. Often, animations are used to show how the product works in virtual environment. However, these animations are not supported by product sounds. If the sound percept is integrated in the presented work, the 3D model would be more realistic and convincing. In this way, by using the pictogram domain and corresponding sounds, industrial designers could model the soundscape of the product, as well. For this, creating a sound library for pictogram groups would be necessary.

Another form of application would be at the sound concept development stage. Designers could use the same sound-pictogram library. By arranging the pictograms (with sounds) on a timeline with relevant psychoacoustical measures, they could design the desired soundscape of a product as a product sound concept proposal.

Discussion: Pictograms for emotions

The above-proposed visual language excludes the emotional impact of sounds. However, the definition of product sound quality suggests that the product sounds elicit emotional responses. Therefore, the experienced emotion evoked by the product sound becomes one of the descriptive attributes of sound and needs to be considered in the design process of a product sound.

Suggested is that pictograms for emotions may represent the emotion domain for product sounds. Desmet (2003) designed a product emotion measurement tool by employing caricaturistic animations of a puppet, which express emotional experience of a product. Van Egmond (2004) used this tool to measure elicited emotions on alarm sounds. It seems possible to use abstract representations (graphical) to express emotions. Furthermore, analyzing the product sound beforehand may enable the sound designer to predict the users' possible emotional responses upon the experienced sound.

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REFERENCES

- Ballas, J. A. 1993. "Common factors in the identification of an assortment of brief everyday sounds." *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 19(2): 250-267.
- Bartlett, J. C. 1977. "Remembering environmental sounds: The role of verbalization at Input." *Memory and Cognition*, 5(4): 404-414.
- von Bismarck, G. 1974. "Timbre of steady sounds: A sactorial investigation of its verbal attributes." *Acustica*, 30: 146 - 159.
- Björk, E. A. 1985. "The perceived quality of natural sounds." *Acustica*, 57: 185-188.
- Blattner, M. M., Sumikawa, D. A., Greenberg, R. M. 1989. "Earcons and Icons: Their Structure and Common Design Principles." *Human Computer Interaction*, 4: 11-44.
- Blauert, J. and Jekosch, U. 1997. "Sound quality evaluation - A multi layered problem." *Acustica*, 83: 747-753.
- Bregman, A. S. 1990. *Auditory scene analysis: The perceptual organization of sound*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: MIT Press.
- Desmet, P. M. A. 2002. *Designing emotions*. Doctoral Dissertation, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands.
- Edworthy, J. and Adams, A.S. 1996. Symbols. In *Warning design: A research prospective*, 75-100. London: Taylor and Francis Ltd.
- Fog, L. and Pedersen, T. 1999. Tools for product optimization. Human Centered Processes 10th Mini EURO Conference. Brest, France.
- Gaver, W. W. 1989. "The SonicFinder: An interface that uses auditory icons." *Human Computer Interaction*, 4: 67-94.
- Gaver, W. W. 1993a. "What in the world do we hear?: An ecological approach to auditory event perception." *Ecological Psychology*, 5(1): 1-29.
- Gaver, W. W. 1993b. "How do we hear in the world?: Explorations in ecological acoustics." *Ecological Psychology*, 5(4): 285-313.
- Hermes, D. J. 1998. "Auditory material perception." *IPO Annual Progress Report*, 33: 95-102.
- Holmes, N. 2000/2001. "Pictograms: A view from the drawing board, or what I have learned from Otto Neurath and Gerd Arntz (and Jazz)." *Information Design Journal*, 10(2): 133-143.
- Kendall, R. A. and Carterette, E. C. 1993. "Verbal attributes of simultaneous wind instrument timbres: I. von Bismarck's Adjectives." *Music Perception*, 10(4): 445-468.

- Klatzky, R. L., Pai, D. K., and Krotkov, E. 2000. "Perception of materials from contact sounds." *Presence*, 9(4): 399-410.
- Kunkler-Peck, A. J., and Turvey, M. T. 2000. "Hearing shape." *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 26(1): 279-294.
- Martens, W. L. and Giragama, C. N. W. 2002. Relating multilingual semantic scales to a common timbre space. 113th Convention of the Audio Engineering Society, Los Angeles, USA.
- McAdams, S. 1993. "Recognition of sound sources and events." In *Thinking in sound: The cognitive psychology of human audition*, edited by McAdams, S. and Bigand, E., 146-198. New York: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Mervis, C. B., and Rosch, L. 1981. "Categorization of natural objects." *Ann. Rev. Psychol.*, 32: 89-115.
- Mynatt, E. D. 1994. Designing with auditory icons: How well do we identify auditory cues? *Chi '94 Conference Companion*, 269-270. New York, NY: ACM.
- Özcan, E., Van Egmond, R., Jacobs, J. 2004. Categorization and identification of product sounds. In progress, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands.
- Solomon, L. N. 1958. "Semantic approach to the perception of complex sounds." *The Journal of the Psychoacoustical Society of America*, 30(5): 421-425.
- Talamo, J. D. C. 1982. "The perception of machinery indicator sounds." *Ergonomics*, 25: 41-51.
- Van Egmond, R. 2004. Emotional experience of frequency modulated sounds: Implications for the design of alarm sounds. In *Human Factors in Design*. edited by D. de Waard, K.A. Brookhuis, and C.M. Weikert. Maastricht, The Netherlands.
- Västfjäll, D., Gulbol, M. A., Kleiner, M., Gärling, T. 2002. "Affective evaluations of and reactions to exterior and interior vehicle auditory quality." *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 255(3): 501-518.
- Zwicker, E. and Fastl, H. 1990. "Sharpness in sensory pleasantness" and "Roughness" In *Psychoacoustics: Facts and Models*, 215-221 and 231-236. Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.

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